

D5.6 Dissemination Activity Report

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

T5.2

Summary

Task description:

The Dissemination and Exploitation task will disseminate the results of the project to the different actors, in particular the Research and Knowledge Sharing community in relation to WP3 and end-user groups such as farmers, foresters and farm advisory services in relation to WP4. This task will utilise established mediums including YouTube, the EIP-AGRI website and dedicated pages of the project website. A formal, dynamic Dissemination and Exploitation Plan will be developed which will be reviewed annually taking into account the output of T3.3. The plan will identify the actors to be targeted at EU, national and regional levels; the key dissemination topics; and the media to be used. Dissemination activities will be implemented targeting the full range of actors with the focus on the end users for which the project is intended to work with. This deliverable reports these dissemination and exploitation activities.

This deliverable reports on the dissemination activities of the EURAKNOS project, outlining the materials created, and channels used to reach target audiences. The EURAKNOS consortium partners have created numerous outputs which have been promoted to relevant target audiences, with special attention on our key outputs: The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks; policy recommendations (the vision paper and policy brief); and the e-KRP in close collaboration with the EUREKA Farmbook. Combined dissemination activities had the potential to reach over 300,000 people. EURAKNOS' Key Exploitable Results are already being successfully exploited in EUREKA, and will be further built upon in a future Horizon Europe funding call. By participating in the Horizon Results Booster Exploitation Strategy Seminar, EURAKNOS has provided a strong foundation including useful considerations for these future projects.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
5.6	WP5
Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(S)
IfA	Laura Palczynski (IfA)
Beneficiaries	Deliverable Co-Author (S)
PSKW, IDELE, USC, NAK, RAU	Sylvia Burssens (UGent)
Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
31/03/2021	31/12/2021

Type of Deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	X
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	

Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Content

List of figures	4
List of tables.....	4
List of abbreviations and acronyms.....	4
Task members	4
1. Introduction.....	5
1.1. Context	5
1.2. Definitions and Objectives.....	6
1.3. Dissemination and Exploitation Report Aims	6
2. Dissemination and Exploitation Goals.....	7
2.1. Main Dissemination Goals.....	7
2.2. Main Exploitation Goals	7
3. Dissemination Outputs	7
3.1. Target Audiences and Key Dissemination Tools and Channels	7
3.2. Dissemination Materials.....	8
4. Dissemination Reporting	12
4.1. The EURAKNOS Website.....	12
4.2. Dissemination Activities	14
4.3. Achievement of Dissemination Indicators.....	16
4.4. Overall evaluation of dissemination performance.....	17
5. Exploitation Activities	18
5.1. Horizon Results Booster: Exploitation Strategy Seminar.....	18
6. Conclusion	22

List of figures

Figure 1 Links between Work Packages (WPs) in the EURAKNOS Project and Task 5.2 Dissemination and Exploitation.....	6
Figure 2a Table of contents on the Deliverables page with navigational links to take the user directly to the relevant heading	12
Figure 2b Example of the identification of different resource types with length and topic indicated	12
Figure 3 Google Analytics data showing number of page views for individual areas of the EURAKNOS website in the period 1 st November 2019-21 st December 2021	13
Figure 4 Google Analytics data showing number of unique page views for the deliverables page of the EURAKNOS website in the period 1st November 2019-21st December 2021, arranged by country ...	13

List of tables

Table 1 Partners involved in the different Tasks of WP5 (task leaders in bold).....	4
Table 2 Key dissemination tools and channels for reaching different target audiences	8
Table 3 List of dissemination outputs	9
Table 4 Achievement of Key Performance Indicators for Dissemination Activities in EURAKNOS	16
Table 5 Characterisation for KER 1. e-KRP. Feedback from Horizon Results Booster contact in green italics.....	19
Table 6 Characterisation for KER 2. The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks	20
Table 7 Issues and Recommendations from Advisors from the Horizon Results Booster ESS.....	21

List of abbreviations and acronyms

AKIS – Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems

D - Deliverable

EC – European Commission

EIP-Agri - Agricultural European Innovation Partnership

ESS – Exploitation Strategy Seminar

EU – Europe/European

EURAKNOS – Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

EUREKA – European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

FAO - The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

FLIN – Farmer Led Innovation Network

KER – Key Exploitable Result

KIP – Knowledge Innovation Panel
KR – Knowledge Reservoir

KE – Knowledge Exchange

MVP – Minimum Viable Product

OG – Operational Group

SCAR – Standing Committee on Agricultural Research

SIB – Strategic Innovation Board

SWG – Strategic Working Group

TN – Thematic Network

WP – Work Package

Task members

Table 1. Partners involved in the different Tasks of WP5 (task leaders in bold).

Task	Partner														
	ACTA	IDELE	NAK	UGent	GLZ	USC	AU	PSKW	ARC	AUA	IFA	LFG	RAU	EV ILVO	IFOA M
5.1	X	X	X			X					X		X		
5.2	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
5.3	X	X	X		X	X	X	X			X		X		
5.4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

1. Introduction

This deliverable outlines the dissemination and exploitation measures and activities conducted over the course of the EURAKNOS project and beyond its funded timeframe.

1.1. Context

EURAKNOS (www.euraknos.eu/) is a Thematic Network (TN) created with the aim to collate and share knowledge from all TNs to build a single community. TNs have the potential to maximise the uptake and impact of new knowledge by stimulating shared learning and coordinating the dissemination of practical information. The overall aim of the EURAKNOS project is to strengthen the EU agricultural knowledgebase by co-creating “the network to connect all thematic networks”.

The main objectives of EURAKNOS are to:

- Develop technical guidelines for building a successful TN based on the multi-actor approach
- Define best dissemination practices (tools, materials, channels...) with high impact on the end-users in particular farmers, foresters and advisors
- To develop a pilot for an open-access EU wide agricultural knowledge innovation system.

To achieve these objectives, EURAKNOS will:

- Facilitate and support TNs, link similar initiatives at EU and national levels and feed into national educational and training programmes;
- Widen and connect existing TNs to build knowledge reservoirs within the agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI);
- Collect, evaluate and compare knowledge, materials and tools that have been produced by TNs and operational groups (OGs);
- Develop a harmonised approach by producing technical guidelines on how to make a high-impact knowledge reservoir;
- Develop a blueprint for creating an EU-wide, dynamic, open-source agricultural knowledge innovation database, and explore the value of doing this.

WP5 aims to communicate, widen and maximise the impact of EURAKNOS outcomes through dedicated communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The specific objectives are:

- To develop detailed and dynamic plans for communication, dissemination and exploitation
- To efficiently communicate the concept, progress and results of EURAKNOS to a wide variety of stakeholders
- To efficiently disseminate EURAKNOS outputs targeted to a variety of actors with a focus on two main groups: (i) TN coordinators as multipliers and (ii) farmers, foresters and advisors
- To provide a wide range of end user materials
- To link educational programs and training initiatives
- To promote cross exchange between different TNs

To achieve these objectives, WP5 is focused on four distinct but inter-related tasks: T5.1 Communication activities, T5.2 Dissemination and Exploitation, T5.3 Networking, and T5.4 Cross-exchange. Together, these tasks foster engagement with policymakers at European (EU) and regional/national levels; the research and knowledge exchange (KE) community; and farmers/foresters, advisors and industry. Communication and networking activities will raise awareness of the project within these groups and the dissemination programme will engage them with the project’s key outputs:

- EURAKNOS Explorer’s Guide to Thematic Networks (WP3)
- The EURAKNOS/EUREKA knowledge platform (WP4)
- Vision Paper and Policy Brief (WP5)

1.2. Definitions and Objectives

This deliverable outlines the dissemination and exploitation measures and activities conducted over the course of the EURAKNOS project, and how these compare with the goals set out in D5.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan. Communication and networking are closely linked with dissemination, but have distinct purposes and activities so are reported separately in D5.5 and D5.7, respectively.

The definitions of dissemination and exploitation, as found in the EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms are as follows:

Dissemination is “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”

Exploitation is “The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”

The European Commission further explains that dissemination aims to transfer knowledge and results to enable others to make use of them, thereby maximising the impact of EU-funded research. Its focus is on describing results and ensuring they are available for others to use; target audience(s) include any group that may take an interest in the potential use of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partners, policymakers). On the other hand, exploitation aims to effectively use project results via scientific, political and/or social exploitation routes to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society. Its focus is on making concrete use of research results, which might be done by people/organisations/user groups from within the consortium, or from outside of the project.

1.3. Dissemination and Exploitation Report Aims

To ensure the impact of EURAKNOS project activities and the results they generate, the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D5.2) identified target audiences, specified channels and media with which to reach them, and established a schedule for dissemination activities based upon outcomes from other work packages (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Links between Work Packages (WPs) in the EURAKNOS Project and Task 5.2 Dissemination and Exploitation

This EURAKNOS Dissemination and Exploitation Report will outline:

- The degree to which the goals and objectives set in D5.2 have been met
- Report on the dissemination of results and the audiences of those activities
- Report on the exploitation of results
- The degree to which the targets set for dissemination and exploitation have been met
- Specify how data generated by the project will be exploited, curated and preserved, even after cessation of the EURAKNOS project.

2. Dissemination and Exploitation Goals

2.1. Main Dissemination Goals

- ✓ Create and share materials including reports, practice abstracts, publications, guidelines, videos and podcasts to make knowledge and results from EURAKNOS available for target end-users
- ✓ Promote and make widely available the guidelines for best practice designed to help guide and streamline the functioning of TNs and other multi-actor projects.
- ✓ Share the prototype e-KRP with accompanying guidelines to demonstrate the potential for a common EU-wide KRP.

2.2. Main Exploitation Goals

- ✓ Ongoing and future TNs, and similar multi-actor projects and initiatives to utilise EURAKNOS recommendations for best practice so that they can work based on the established knowledge from past and current TNs so that the successes and imperfections experienced in previous projects can be learnt from and built upon.
- ✓ The EURAKNOS e-KRP prototype and recommendations to guide relevant governing/funding bodies and projects/initiatives to develop a full-scale, self-sustainable EU-wide open source KRP for TN outputs and knowledge to be collectively stored for easy access by end- users.

3. Dissemination Outputs

3.1. Target Audiences and Key Dissemination Tools and Channels

The primary audience for EURAKNOS outputs is the Research and Knowledge Sharing community who act as multipliers, particularly actors participating in TNs, multi-actor projects and linked to OGs. The results from EURAKNOS will help these actors/projects to communicate and collaborate more effectively with their end-users – farmers, foresters, agricultural advisors and educators, and students. The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks is a key resource for this group.

The findings from EURAKNOS are also of interest to policymakers at national and European levels, national rural networks, organisations with similar initiatives, and actors associated with educational programmes and training, as well as funding bodies to help identify potential areas for improvement to existing systems and practices and inform budget allocation. The technical guidelines and prototype for the e-KRP and policy recommendations are key resources for these groups.

Target audiences and relevant key dissemination tools and channels to reach them are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Key dissemination tools and channels for reaching different target audiences

Target Audience	Tools	Channels
Research Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research articles • Public deliverables • e-KRP prototype 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Access publications • EURAKNOS Website • Networking e.g. research institutes • Webinars
Knowledge Sharing Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice abstracts • Research articles • Videos • Podcasts • Public deliverables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EIP-AGRI • Open Access publications • EURAKNOS Website • Networking e.g. KIP, SIB • Webinars
TN Consortia Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice abstracts • Research articles • Videos • Podcasts • Public deliverables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EIP-AGRI • Open Access publications • EURAKNOS Website • Networking e.g. KIP • Webinars
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision paper • Policy brief • e-KRP prototype 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizon Results Platform • EURAKNOS Website • Networking e.g. SIB, NRNs • Webinars
Education/Training Institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice abstracts • Videos • Podcasts • Research articles • e-KRP prototype 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EIP-AGRI • EURAKNOS Website • Open Access publications • Networking e.g. national education/training bodies, colleges, universities • Webinars

3.2. Dissemination Materials

The EURAKNOS project produced 20 public deliverables (Table 3), with key findings presented in various formats and made available on our website:

- ✓ EURAKNOS has produced **100 practice abstracts**, which are in the process of being made available via EIP-Agri. The first 20 PAs from D5.10 were converted to an attractive format, and images were shared on social media.
- ✓ The **policy brief** and **vision paper** have been added to [the Horizon Results Platform](#), and were heavily featured in our final EURAKNOS webinars and will continue to be presented by consortium partners beyond the end of the project's funded period.
- ✓ **5 videos** were produced to present the EURAKNOS project and its results, hosted on [YouTube](#). Two videos were recorded at the Budapest workshop in 2019. Three animated videos present key outcomes from WP2 (Best practices for TNs), WP3 (Introducing the Explorer's Guide) and WP4 (Building a digital knowledge database). In addition, recordings from the final EURAKNOS webinars are available as 6 videos (1 per session).
- ✓ **50 podcasts** were produced and hosted on [Spotify](#) and YouTube. Of these, 27 disseminated findings from EURAKNOS, 23 communicated about other TN projects.
- ✓ **The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks** is the culmination of WP2 and WP3 work summarizing recommendations co-created with actors involved in TNs. It is available, digitally or as a printed copy, in 13 languages (English, Danish, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Lithuanian, Romanian, Slovenian, and Spanish). Following the EURAKNOS webinar on 5th February 2021, an external actor has translated it to Polish and we are working towards a final formatted version.
- ✓ **The prototype e-KRP – FarmBook**, developed in collaboration with the EUREKA project, was presented in the final EURAKNOS webinars. The TN and AKIS community, as well as policymakers, are very interested in its development and associated technical guidelines.

Table 3 List of dissemination outputs

Deliverable	Dissemination Outputs	Target Audience	Key Message	Key Channels
D2.1 Data and Knowledge Formats of TNs	2 Practice Abstracts Explorer's Guide	Ongoing and future TNs	Comparisons of the ways in which TNs produce, collect and store knowledge, considering TN origin, content, format and synergies	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI Service Point
D2.2 KR Design of TNs	3 Practice Abstracts Explorer's Guide	Ongoing and future TNs	Describing the format and design of KRs developed by existing TNs and related recommendations for consistency and improved impact.	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D2.3 C&D methods of TNs	6 Practice Abstracts Explorer's Guide	Ongoing and future TNs; Agriculture Advisory Services and Educational Institutions	Mapping the practices used by past and present TNs and analysing their success at reaching farmers, foresters and end-users. Recommendations for more efficient C&D via appropriate tools and channels for improved impact.	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D2.4 MAA of TNs	6 Practice Abstracts Explorer's Guide	Ongoing and future TNs; Agriculture Advisory Services; Educational Institutions	Mapping the methods used by past and present TNs to incorporate the MAA to outline best practices.	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D2.5 Budapest Workshop Report	20 Practice Abstracts 20 recommendations Policy Brief	Ongoing and future TNs; Agriculture Advisory Services and Educational Institutions	20 recommendations based on the ideas and experiences from TNs relating to content, content storage, C&D, and the MAA	EURAKNOS website Email to KIP/SIB/SWG SCAR AKIS networks
D2.6 Summary of TN Practices	7 Practice Abstracts Summary of the indicators Explorer's Guide	Ongoing and future TNs; Agriculture Advisory Services and Educational Institutions	Quantitative and Qualitative indicators related to the content, design, C&D, MAA to achieve a higher impact in terms of uptake of results by the end-user, farmer, forester, and advisor	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D3.1 HIKR Data Management	3 Practice Abstracts Explorer's Guide Book Chapter	Ongoing and future TNs; KRP developers	Identification of the processes used to compile knowledge content in their knowledge reservoir and then disseminate it to end-users.	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D3.2 HIKR Design	4 Practice Abstracts Book Chapter	Ongoing and future TNs; Agriculture Advisory Services; Educational Institutions; National Rural Networks; KRP developers	A strategy to move from the HIKR to the e-KRP, including recommendations for how to attain a user-friendly and accessible digital platform.	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D3.3 HIKR CD&E	6 Practice Abstracts Explorer's Guide	Ongoing and future TNs; Agriculture Advisory Services	Framework to support strategic decision making plus recommendations and examples of good practice for dissemination and exploitation tools and channels.	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI

D3.4 HIKR MAA	9 Practice Abstracts Explorer's Guide	Ongoing and future TNs; Agriculture Advisory Services	Recommendations to foster the multi-actor approach in all project activities	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D3.5 Tallinn Workshop Report	Explorer's Guide	TN projects, OGs and similar initiatives, KRP developers; policymakers	How to design and implement TNs to maximise user engagement and impact. A support framework to learn from previous TNs, reflect and implement the most relevant elements to create higher impact	EURAKNOS website Email to KIP/SIB networks
D3.6 HIKR Technical Guidelines	TN Explorer's Guide 12 Practice Abstracts	TN projects, OGs and similar initiatives, KRP developers; policymakers	How to design and implement TNs to maximise user engagement and impact. A support framework to learn from previous TNs, reflect and implement the most relevant elements to create higher impact	EURAKNOS website Email to KIP/SIB networks EIP-AGRI Networking events and EURAKNOS Webinars
D4.1 e-KRP Feasibility and Added Value	2 Practice Abstracts Book Chapter	TN projects, Educational Institutions; National Rural Networks; KRP developers; policymakers	Identification of the needs of the different potential e-KRP user types for knowledge objects	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D4.2 API Documentation	3 Practice Abstracts Book Chapter	KRP developers; policymakers	Explanation of what metadata are and their importance. Description and explanation of the metadata properties (and the values they can receive) that have been defined for the annotation of the data objects stored into the EURAKNOS repository.	EURAKNOS website EIP-AGRI
D4.3 e-KRP Prototype Guide	PowerPoint Slides Book Chapter	KRP developers; policymakers	Presentation and explanation of the role and functioning of the modules of the platform. Description and explanation (in an easy-to-comprehend) way of the technologies solutions adopted.	EURAKNOS website Email to KIP/SIB networks Networking events and EURAKNOS Webinars
D4.4 Future Vision for e-KRP	2 Practice Abstracts PowerPoint Slides	KRP developers; policymakers	Presentation of the visuals and screens within the scope of the prototype. Description of the desires and wishes of potential end users for the future platform beyond the scope of prototype.	EURAKNOS website Networking events and EURAKNOS Webinars EIP-AGRI

Various	25 Podcasts and 9 videos	Ongoing and future TNs; National Rural Networks; Agriculture Advisory Services; Educational Institutions	3 animated videos based on results from WPs, plus 6 recorded sessions from the final EURAKNOS Webinars. 25 podcasts focused on disseminating results	EURAKNOS website; Spotify/ YouTube
D5.8 Vision Paper	Vision Paper	Policymakers; TNs; National Rural Networks; International Organisations; Similar projects /initiatives	Addresses the question: <i>What should an open source KR for agriculture and forestry look like, and what do we need and want from it?</i> Discusses achieving high impact, end-user needs and ways to attain a self-sustaining system for longevity	EURAKNOS website Horizon Results Platform Networking events and EURAKNOS Webinars
D5.9 Policy Brief	Policy Brief	Policymakers; government institutions, advisory groups, decision-making bodies	Creating awareness of the best practices and methodologies for TNs and the creation of a common EU knowledge reservoir. Guidelines for policymakers on TNs, the MAA, and on the creation of a knowledge reservoir (including at national level)	EURAKNOS website Horizon Results Platform Networking events and EURAKNOS Webinars
Various	Cross Exchange Visits	Ongoing and future TNs, OGs, farmers, foresters and advisors	Individual cross-exchange visits incorporating results from WPs and linking with other TN projects (See D5.4)	Digital meetings
D5.10/11 Practice Abstracts	100 practice abstracts/ summary factsheets	Ongoing and future TNs, National Rural Networks; Educational Institutions and/or farmers and foresters depending on topic	Individual practice abstracts based on results from WPs (Table 2) and relating to various topics (See D5.10)	EURAKNOS website EIP Agri
Various	Networking Activities	Ongoing and future TNs; similar MA initiatives and projects; Educational Institutions; National Rural Networks	Opportunities to highlight key EURAKNOS outputs and share dissemination materials (See D5.3)	Calls, emails, face-to-face, or digital meetings.
Various	5 Research Articles (not yet published)	Scientific Community	TN content; TN C&D (WP2) History of AKIS (WP2) Dissemination & Impact (WP3) MMA (WP3)	Publication in Open Access Journal

4. Dissemination Reporting

4.1. The EURAKNOS Website

The EURAKNOS website is one of the key channels for dissemination of the project's outputs. The [Deliverables page](#) hosts all EURAKNOS information resources: all public deliverables and related outputs are available, arranged under the following headings, which are described with navigational links in a table of contents (Figure 2a):

- The Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks
- Policy Recommendations
- e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform
- TN Learnings
- About EURAKNOS
- Our TN Network

Each of these sections contains different resource types (e.g. webinars, videos, podcasts, guides, reports) which are clearly identified with their length and topic to help the user to choose the most relevant information materials to suit their wants and needs (Figure 2b).

Figure 2a Table of contents on the Deliverables page with navigational links to take the user directly to the relevant heading.

Figure 2b Example of the identification of different resource types with length and topic indicated.

As shown in Figure 3, the Deliverables page was the fourth-most visited area of the EURAKNOS website after the homepage, the about page, and TN page, receiving 1,344 unique page views between November 2019 and December 2021. These figures do not include direct links to deliverables for which we have no data available, as this function is not available through Google Analytics so number of direct downloads of deliverables is unknown. Links direct to resources were often used in email communications and social media posts so it is likely that we reached more users than indicated by Google Analytics data alone. The average time spent on the deliverables page was much higher than for other pages, indicating that visitors took the time to browse the resources available for download and suggesting a positive outreach from the project.

Furthermore, the deliverables page of the website was visited by users from 56 different countries. Presented in Figure 4 are the 27 countries represented by 5 or more unique visitors. This indicates that EURAKNOS resources have been viewed internationally beyond the EU Member States represented by the EURAKNOS project consortium, extending the reach of the project.

Page	Pageviews	Unique Pageviews	Avg. Time on Page	Entrances
	22,371 % of Total: 100.00% (22,371)	16,367 % of Total: 100.00% (16,367)	00:01:24 Avg for View: 00:01:24 (0.00%)	9,890 % of Total: 100.00% (9,890)
1. /	11,791 (52.71%)	8,196 (50.08%)	00:01:24	7,920 (80.08%)
2. /about	2,238 (10.00%)	1,776 (10.85%)	00:01:30	483 (4.88%)
3. /thematic-network	1,884 (8.42%)	1,441 (8.80%)	00:01:39	361 (3.65%)
4. /deliverables	1,661 (7.42%)	1,344 (8.21%)	00:02:23	371 (3.75%)
5. /news	1,433 (6.41%)	919 (5.61%)	00:00:38	125 (1.26%)
6. /events	636 (2.84%)	538 (3.29%)	00:01:01	60 (0.61%)
7. /cev	230 (1.03%)	204 (1.25%)	00:01:12	19 (0.19%)

Figure 3 Google Analytics data showing number of page views for individual areas of the EURAKNOS website in the period 1st November 2019-21st December 2021. The deliverables page had the longest average time spent on the page by users compared to other areas of the website.

Figure 4 Google Analytics data showing number of unique page views for the deliverables page of the EURAKNOS website in the period 1st November 2019-21st December 2021.

4.1.1. Reflections on the EURAKNOS Website

EURAKNOS faced similar challenges as those experienced by previous TN projects, as presented in D2.2, and the recommendations for effective storage and presentation of information resources on project websites was not available before month 10. It was important for communication efforts that the website was functional much earlier in the project (M3), however, this poses challenges for web design. The cheapest, easiest and most efficient way to build a website is to have a clear map outlining the required webpage structure. Web developers require a clear web tree mapping all required areas on the website, and it can be difficult to foresee how to allow easy access to resources before tangible outputs exist. It is not desirable to have a website containing dead links whilst work towards completing deliverables is conducted so compromises must be made. This makes balancing the time,

finance and project workstreams difficult to manage. One EURAKNOS partner (LeapForward) had the relevant skills and expertise for web design, development and maintenance; however, they were also heavily involved in other tasks and WPs so had finite resources available to them, especially in terms of personnel time, so they were limited in their ability to alter the website structure later in the project. Rather than a long list of resources under the deliverables heading, it would have been nice for each category to have its own sub-page which could be easily navigated to, with searchable resources. However, the effort that would be required to achieve this was not possible within the budgetary constraints of the project. A compromise was made to arrange the resources under headings with a contents list (Figure 2a).

It was anticipated that the project website would be translated into different European languages, at least for those countries represented by the project consortium partners. However, this commitment was made under the understanding that free software could be easily incorporated into the website structure to enable easy translation, which was not the case. As of January 2019, the Google Translate widget ceased being available for use by new websites and a suitable alternative could not be identified. Furthermore, these tools would only translate the text in the body of the webpage, it would not translate the information resources themselves. This is a major challenge faced by all projects – if translations are required, it needs substantial time and/or money for partners or an external service to translate the documents. In EURAKNOS, it was felt that the Explorer’s Guide was a compilation of our key findings and recommendations, so we opted to translate this resource into 12 EU languages in addition to English. Furthermore, some partners opted to translate resources if they were particularly relevant to their activities. For example, the vision paper and policy brief were translated to Estonian by ARC/PMK. Until high quality, affordable automated translation software/services are developed and widely available, TNs like EURAKNOS will continue to struggle to meet the requirement for translation.

4.2. Dissemination Activities

Specific information regarding the reach of the materials that were created is limited, so estimations must be used as proxy indicators. Communication and networking activities reported in D5.5. and D5.7, respectively are also relevant to dissemination.

Key dissemination activities include:

- ✓ **Publication of the vision paper and policy brief** – these documents were made freely available on the EURAKNOS website, in addition:
 - ARC/PMK actively translated and promoted the vision paper and policy brief with relevant Estonian organisations who shared these documents via their mailing lists, websites and social media, achieving an estimated reach of 10,000 persons.
 - IfA shared the vision paper on social media with a potential reach of 6500 to an audience of farmers and advisors, researchers and policymakers.
 - USC shared the vision paper and policy brief via AFINET’s social media channels, achieving a potential reach of 1,400 amongst farmers and advisors, researchers and policymakers; they also shared with Spain’s National Rural Network via webinar, reaching 100 persons.
- ✓ **A book chapter**, *Integrating Agriculture-Related Data Provided by Thematic Networks into a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir*, authored by: Hercules Panoutsopoulos, Borja Espejo Garcia, Philip E. G. Verbist, Spyros Fountas, Pieter Spanoghe, and Christopher Brewster. The chapter will be published in *Modeling for Sustainable Management in Agriculture, Food and the Environment*, edited by George Vlontzos, Yiannis Ampatzidis, Basil Manos, and Panos M. Pardalos. The publisher is Routledge. Details about the volume and its book chapters are available at [here](#), book will be on sale from September 2021.
- ✓ **5 research papers** are being prepared with the aim to be published later in 2021 or 2022:
 - *The Multi-Actor Approach in Thematic Networks for Agriculture and Forestry Innovation:* Currently under review in *Agricultural and Food Economics*
 - *The Relevance of Videos as a Practical Tool for Communication and Dissemination in*

Horizon2020 Thematic Networks: [Published in Sustainability journal](#)

- *The history of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System and its implementation in the European Union context:* In progress
- *Evaluating the knowledge content produced by European Thematic Network Projects:* In process
- *Evaluating communication and dissemination methods in European Thematic Network Projects:* In progress
- ✓ **Presentation of the Key Outputs of EURAKNOS Webinar** – The first of two final webinars hosted by EURAKNOS attracted 150 participants across the three sessions which focused on conveying key messages from: the Explorer’s Guide, the vision paper and policy brief, and presenting the EURAKNOS/EUREKA Farmbook e-KRP prototype. The recorded sessions have been viewed 45 times on YouTube.
- ✓ **EURAKNOS Final Conference Webinar** – The final webinar hosted by EURAKNOS attracted 109 participants across the three sessions which focused on conveying key messages to specific target groups: (i) those with a general interest, (ii) the TN, KE and AKIS community, and (iii) policymakers. The recorded sessions have been viewed 59 times on YouTube.
- ✓ **National Webinars** – As reported in D5.7, several partners conducted events in their own national language to promote EURAKNOS results.
- ✓ **Sharing the EURAKNOS Explorer’s Guide to Thematic Networks** the consortium has been actively sharing the EURAKNOS Explorer’s Guide within their networks, for example:
 - IfA promoted the Explorer’s Guide via newsletter (1400 reach) and social media (potential reach 6500) to an audience of farmers and advisors, researchers and policymakers. In addition, they directly emailed 60 contacts to inform them of the digital resource and offer printed copies, 9 of these individuals requested printed copies. In addition, 6 copies with cover letters were posted to UK Agri-Tech Centres (<https://agri-epicentre.com/>) and 1 copy to the contact for agriculture at Telecommunications Software and Systems Group in Ireland (<https://tssg.org/industry/>) to promote the multi actor approach.
 - EUREKA consortium partners were also involved in assisting with the translation of the Explorer’s guide. For example, KIS circulated the Slovenian version of the guide to research institutions (institutes and faculties), the ministry of agriculture, the Chamber of agriculture and advisory service and two faculties in Croatia.
 - RAU disseminated the Explorer’s Guide via email to the Farmer Led Innovation Network (FLIN) members (approx. 1500 farmers involved in farmer-led innovation across the UK and over 20 organisations including governmental and non-governmental organisations, research institutes, the national levy board, farmer organisations and advisory services). In April 2021 RAU disseminated the Explorers Guide at an online training workshop for 10 regional facilitators of the Pasture Fed Livestock Association who bring farmers together to facilitate their knowledge exchange to transition towards regenerative farming practices <https://www.pastureforlife.org/>.
 - IFOAM shared the EURAKNOS Explorer’s Guide several times as a news article on the Organics Europe website, social media channels and newsletter.
 - AU/ICROFS promoted the Explorer’s Guide via website articles and social media, achieving a potential reach of 1500 in Denmark, including farmers and advisors, researchers and policymakers.
 - USC shared the Explorer’s Guide via AFINET’s social media channels, achieving a potential reach of 1,400 amongst farmers and advisors, researchers and policymakers; they also shared with Spain’s National Rural Network via webinar, reaching 100 persons.
 - NAK shared the translated, printed Explorer’s Guide and policy recommendations to the Chief Directorate on Agricultural Modernisation and the Agricultural Deputy Assistant Secretary of State in Hungary.

- ✓ UGent will present the vision and recommendations for the e-KRP in December 2021 at a webinar organized by The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation (FAO) in which a variety of actors will be present (representatives from advisors/farmers organisations, policymakers at national and regional level etc).

Despite the efforts of the consortium to promote EURAKNOS outputs, the short timeframe for EURAKNOS (2 years 3 months) meant that the project experienced similar challenges to those experienced by other TNs which were reported in D2.3 - partners had limited time and resources available to disseminate results with the majority of effort spent on generating results, with little remaining time or budget to present them in an attractive, user-friendly format and also share and promote the resources widely within the target audience. Furthermore, the challenges presented by COVID-19 restrictions meant that unforeseen time and effort was dedicated to changing plans and adapting to digital approaches to dissemination.

4.3. Achievement of Dissemination Indicators

The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D5.2) outlined several key performance indicators in terms of numbers of target actors reached through different dissemination activities. The achievement of these goals is included in Table 4.

Table 4 Achievement of Key Performance Indicators for Dissemination Activities in EURAKNOS

Impact Indicator: Number of	Target Reach:			Achievement
	Per Country	In Europe	Globally	
TN actors reached through the EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks	100	2 800	-	Widely promoted through networking events(D5.7), social media (D5.5) and direct contact from partners. These activities potentially reached over 10,000 people.
Policymakers reached through vision paper	10	280	20	Widely promoted via partner networks, e.g. ARC/PMK potentially reached 10,000 persons in Estonia. NAK contacted Hungarian policymakers by disseminating results via their newsletter, website and social media channels, but also the Hungarian Website of EIP-Agri. Presented at the final webinars which were attended by approx. 250 people.
Policymakers reached through SCAR AKIS policy brief	10	280	20	Partners promoted the policy brief within their own networks. Promotion of the recommendations at our final webinars attended by approx. 250 people. Also uploaded to the Horizon Results Platform
International organisations reached	-	-	10	Our SIB includes representatives from global organisations The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and Global Open Data for Agriculture & Nutrition. Networking activities (D5.7) reached some international organisations.
TNs involved through consortium KIP, SIB	-	34 + new TNs	-	All current TNs (33 + EURAKNOS) are featured on the EURAKNOS website and receive updates via the EURAKNOS newsletter, social media and invited to participate in cross-exchanges. The earliest 28 TNs were involved in WP2 and 3 data collection and workshops, some of these also feature in Podcasts.
Advisors, farmers, foresters reached by participation in major agricultural fairs and conferences	-	2 500	-	Impacted due to COVID-19, but EURAKNOS partners presented at digital events with more than 1800 participants reached through 74 activities including 17 CEVs
Researchers, policymakers, advisors, farmers, foresters reached via social media	-	-	25 000	According to D5.5, across Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook, EURAKNOS has potentially reached 60,000 persons.

EU policymakers, agri-business, managing authorities, researchers, policymakers, advisors, farmers, foresters reached by the EURAKNOS website	-	15 000	-	Over its lifetime, the EURAKNOS website achieved a total of 16,367 unique page views . These figures do not include direct access to resources.
Researchers, policymakers, advisors, agribusiness, farmers, foresters reached by the EURAKNOS newsletter	-	1000	-	The EURAKNOS newsletter, available in 10 languages, has 447 subscribers , average number of readers per newsletter was 108. These figures do not include the availability of the newsletter on the website, nor people reached through email forwarding.

4.4. Overall evaluation of dissemination performance

Overall, EURAKNOS achieved its intended purpose. It became a well-recognised project within the TN community, as indicated by the TN network's participation in workshops and podcasts. There was a lot of interest in the concept EURAKNOS was working towards, but also some disappointment that the end goal for this project was to establish a proof-of-concept for a common e-KRP rather than a fully functional platform to help solve the issue of sustaining project networks and results beyond the funded period. It is fortunate that [EUREKA](#) is building upon the work of EURAKNOS to develop a functional prototype – the 'FarmBook'. This will be discussed further in the next section about exploitation.

With a critical eye, at the project proposal stage there appeared to be some confusion about the target audiences for EURAKNOS. Whilst it was critical to include farmers and foresters in the workshops and other activities aiming to understand the requirements for a user-friendly e-KRP, they were not an appropriate target audience for dissemination. The results from EURAKNOS are much more relevant to TN consortia partners, policy makers and AKIS communities to show the added value of an e-KRP and share knowledge about how to design and implement thematic networks (and other projects/advisory services) to maximise user engagement and impact. For these audiences, the networking activities reported in D5.7 are especially relevant. Opportunities provided by EIP-AGRI, the European Commission and national governments to facilitate the integration of policymakers with project representatives are hugely beneficial. However, travel restrictions due to COVID-19 hindered EURAKNOS' dissemination efforts tremendously, although many digital opportunities were taken by partners to promote EURAKNOS and its work.

EURAKNOS, like many other projects, failed to allocate sufficient time for dissemination activities during the project proposal. Deliverable reports, though listed as public are often not particularly informative nor attractive for an external audience, e.g. using jargon terms and abbreviations. The style of the deliverable reports for EURAKNOS could have been improved to be more user-friendly, or key excerpts could have been selected to be featured in an attractive 'factsheet' format – this was the initial plan in D5.2, but it was not achieved in practice as partners expended their budgeted personnel time on producing the deliverable reports and were reluctant to spend more time developing user-friendly materials.

Finding time for dissemination was particularly challenging as EURAKNOS was only funded for 2 years (plus 3 months due to a no-cost extension due to the challenges posed by COVID-19 restrictions). Dissemination materials were developed late in the project – this is the case for many projects because a lot of 'background' work and time is needed to generate results and produce deliverable reports, then more time to create attractive dissemination formats for the user, then even more time to promote these user-friendly resources. This later stage of dissemination material production and promotion is often underbudgeted both in terms of time and money, as was the case in EURAKNOS. This could indicate that another project 'phase' is required where experimental work is concluded, but funding remains in place for project partners to focus on dissemination and exploitation of those findings, which might include translation of results. Further work is needed to explore these challenges and potential solutions.

5. Exploitation Activities

The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks

- ✓ The Explorer's Guide has been widely promoted, and positive feedback has been received from those involved in TNs, and especially those who are new to the EU-funded project sphere.
- ✓ In September 2021 – January 2022 RAU will embed the Explorer's Guide as a best practice case study for co-creating knowledge and knowledge exchange within a new teaching module – [The Theory and practice of knowledge exchange](#). This module is being taught in the second year (Level 5) of a BSc (Hons) in Environment, Food and Society. This module will also showcase the EURAKNOS videos and podcasts as a means of teaching the process of facilitating thematic networks.
- ✓ Following the final EURAKNOS conference in February 2021, a participant asked to translate the Explorer's Guide into Polish as she felt it was such a valuable resource. The translation is complete and there are plans to work together to enter it into the attractive pdf format in September 2021.

The e-KRP vision, design and proof of concept

- ✓ The [EUREKA project](#), running from 1st January 2020 until the end of 2021 is already building on the experience of EURAKNOS to work with all multi-actor projects (not only TNs) and develop a working prototype of the e-KRP: the FarmBook.
- ✓ The EURAKNOS/EUREKA FarmBook platform has received much interest from the EU community, from those involved in projects to policymakers.
- ✓ There will be a future funding call within Horizon Europe to further build upon the work of EURAKNOS and EUREKA. This call will be for 7-years of funding to develop the platform from a minimum viable product into a fully-fledged and operational system.
- ✓ These recommendations are complimentary to the modernization of national strategic plans for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) which will require stronger collaboration between multiple actors and efforts in digitalization. They have been promoted with relevant national initiatives/governments, competent authorities, CAP networks and AKIS coordination bodies to assist with e.g. interoperable IT language, formats, user-friendliness and FAIR principles. These results might be utilized by EIP-Agri Service point.

5.1. Horizon Results Booster: Exploitation Strategy Seminar

EURAKNOS participated in the Horizon Results Booster Exploitation Strategy Seminar (ESS), an initiative of the European Commission, beginning the 25th January 2021. Two main products with a set of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) were identified:

- (i) the design/technical guidelines and proof-of-concept for the e-KRP
- (ii) the Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks

The ESS meetings themselves were attended by representatives from IfA, ACTA, and UGent, but after the first meeting where the exercises were presented, an internal meeting was held with IfA, ACTA, UGent, LFG, AUA and IDELE to discuss the details of the KERs. A representative of HCC from the WP leader for communication and dissemination from the EUREKA project was also invited to join the discussions as the results would be highly valuable for EUREKA. The final report was also shared with the EUREKA project so that the consortium can consider its content in their exploitation plan for the FarmBook.

Table 5 and Table 6 shows a shortened version of the characterisation table for the e-KRP and EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks, respectively. These tables outline the problem we seek to address with the KER, the description and unique selling point of our KER, and target market for the KER. Table 7 summarises the issues and recommendations identified by the advisors from Horizon Results Booster.

Table 5 Characterisation for KER 1. e-KRP. Feedback from Horizon Results Booster contact in green italics

KER No.1 - e-KRP	
Problem	<p>TNs have a limited funded period, resulting in a lack of sustainability for their results. Furthermore, each TN uses different metadata – there is no uniform way to describe data/knowledge outputs, it is very project/topic-specific. The range of storage solutions means results of TNs are not easy to find and access by end-users. The proof-of-concept e-KRP offers a solution to give a standardised format for storing outputs that can be accessed from one location. The problem definition is based on TN Coordinators' feedback and observations.</p> <p><i>Are we facing market push or market pull? Because depending on this your strategy will be different</i></p> <p>There is much interest from the EU project community in this solution, so this could indicate market pull.</p>
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<p>Can provide a unique entry point for knowledge (rather than looking for a specific project/topic) so ultimately makes information easier to find.</p> <p>Offers structure for building a knowledge library by outlining consistent metadata. Specific knowledge object categories have been identified with specific types per category. This means this e-KRP can provide a breadth of different object types compared to existing systems.</p> <p>Adoption of SoA open source technologies in the design provides solutions relating to scaling up and security.</p>
Description	e-KRP: vision, design, proof of concept which can be further developed and applied. In the first instance, this work will be built on in the EUREKA project; there will be a funding call in Horizon Europe to scale up further.
"Market" – Target market	<p>Ultimately: farmers, foresters, advisors, and educators – practitioners will use the full-scale platform (users). Primary: TNs and MAA projects to house knowledge objects on the platform (contributors-potential consumers). Policymakers to support this system. Secondary: Organisations/companies etc. that will build on design to scale up to functional e-KRP</p> <p><i>The concept of market is different from the concept of user – when talking about market we are referring to users who are willing to pay to get access to the solution, is this the case?</i></p> <p><i>If this is not the case who will pay for that (apart from a new funding round, which however cannot continue forever)?</i></p> <p><i>Do you think this is something that will change in the future? The potential difference between users and customers (who pays for the service) must be highlighted very clearly in the characterization table as it will heavily influence the exploitation strategy and actions.</i></p> <p>The aim is to create a valuable, centralized service so suggest the EC or other government bodies could own and maintain the system. Advertising is an unattractive option as would detract from user-friendliness of the platform. A more indirect route for receiving state funding would be for projects to pay a subscription fee to host their results on the platform, but official EC products and services should not charge fees for publication.</p>
"Market" - Competitors	<p>e-KRP: Local-level solutions e.g. Lithuanian solution https://titris.lzukt.lt/en/applications/all, organic farm knowledge platform https://organic-farmknowledge.org/. CORDIS, EIP-Agri, EU projects</p> <p><i>Do you know how these competitors are funding their activities? Who pays for the platforms? Who are the users of the platforms?</i></p> <p>Unsure, but appear largely to be government-funded.</p>

Table 6 Characterisation for KER 2. The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks

KER No. 2 – Explorer's Guide	
Problem	TNs are a very specific type of network. Although some principles and practices are common with other networks, there is a lack of guidance on how to approach TN project proposals and execution. TNs are a policy tool that are oriented to networking of OGs so OGs want to understand TN function at capacity level – networking across borders is a specific objective of TNs. The EG focuses upon the specific characteristics of TNs and provides a great toolbox and insight into TNs for more effective involvement of a range of users across different countries. The EG is a fundamental contribution to understanding the concept of Horizon-funded TNs.
Alternative solution	Ad hoc, different approaches of TNs – effectiveness and efficacy of different practices questionable – some good examples have been replicated e.g. cross visits. Repetition in organisations in successful consortia/coordinator roles.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	Compiles learning/experiences from all TNs in one place. Suggests possible approaches for how to manage a TN: reflection tool for choosing TN approaches that will fit your project/timeline. Reflection tool for choosing relevant actors/users/stakeholders to involve in MAA. Guidance for new projects and those who want to learn more about TN function to get involved.
Description	Available in a range of EU languages, online and in print, this guide offers clear examples and explanations for running TNs. It is a social good with no commercial ends.
"Market" – <i>Target market</i>	New TNs, EC/Horizon Europe to recommend guidelines for new projects. This is a social good for non-commercial purposes and the target market is all groups wishing to create a new TN but also useful for every TNs (old and new).
"Market" - Competitors	EC guidelines, LIASON, Nefertiti (other projects), Fabulous Farmers
Go to Market – Use model	Recommendations included as part of Horizon Europe TN calls Applied in EUREKA (and other TNs).

The EUREKA project is ongoing and is able to incorporate these suggestions; the final ESS report was shared with the EUREKA project with key points highlighted in the accompanying email. EURAKNOS' response to specific recommendations from the ESS are included in Table 7.

Table 7 Issues and Recommendations from Advisors from the Horizon Results Booster ESS

Issues	Recommendations
Characterisation of KERs	<p>Two main products with a set of KERs were considered at the online ESS. The discussion was very participative. The seminar helped to focus on the main aspects to be considered in the future elaboration of EURAKNOS.</p> <p>Considering that there is almost no time to address exploitation, it is recommended that the Exploitation Leading Partner makes sure that what was discussed during the seminar is well documented, included in final deliverable, presented as starting point for the next part of the project.</p> <p>Response: This has been done, the WP leader for communication and dissemination in EUREKA was involved in the discussions about KERs and the final report was shared with them. They are considering these inputs in developing their business model for the FarmBook.</p>
New KER Policy Recommendation	<p>During the ESS it became evident that the platform and guidelines created thanks to the H2020 call would be very beneficial to researchers and innovators that are part of a Thematic Network and to TNs themselves to provide an additional boost to their visibility. In this phase the Platform might need some support from the EC, that might take the form for example of suggesting making use of the platform in future relevant Horizon Europe calls. This could create a flow of funds required to sustain the exploitation of the platform until it has obtained enough visibility that will generate autonomous traction and turnover.</p> <p>To ensure the quality and relevance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Engage early conversation with EC to determine which will be the option considered for the Platform (part of EC, new unit or completely outsourced) 2) Present the EG and the platform to new networks and other relevant associations/networks who could disseminate the platform among their members (e.g. EBN – www.ebn.eu – or EURADA - www.eurada.org) and participate in any info day or other type of such events, to promote the platform. Self-promote the EG by uploading it into the platform. 3) Analyse and communicate uncertainty and diverging views related to management and the possibility to generate revenues (commercial ads in the platform/subscription fees or free and open without commercials) <p>Response: Partners involved in both EURAKNOS and EUREKA consortia are continuing to promote and discuss the concept of the eKRP through participation and presentation at relevant events and conferences.</p>
Discussing Exploitation at Consortium Meetings	<p>As this seminar came at the end of the current project, we recommend to include discussing exploitation at consortium meetings in the recommendations to the existing follow up project (EUREKA) and to the other follow ups that could come under Horizon Europe.</p> <p>Response: This has been done.</p>
Horizon Results Platform	<p>It is strongly suggested for Dissemination purposes to upload each key Exploitable result on the EC Horizon Results Platform https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform</p> <p>Response: This is in process.</p>

5.2. Other Exploitation activities

The data management plan (D1.10) contains information about the licensing of key EURAKNOS outputs and their availability on Open-Source Platforms to ensure results remain available beyond the EURAKNOS website and project funding.

The policy recommendations (Vision Paper and Policy Brief) are also exploitable results which partners have been promoting at events and conferences since the funded period of EURAKNOS has concluded. These have been added to the Horizon Results Platform, categorised as policy-related results.

The EURAKNOS Explorer's guide has been translated to Polish by a third party and EURAKNOS partners continue to make use of the guide in their activities:

- AU/ICROFS are project officers for the Danish organic agriculture research program, [Organic RDD](#). Every year (if COVID-19 permits), they have a meeting with project leaders/participants representing all types of stakeholders (around 50 participants, 30-70 years of age: researchers, advisors, representatives from farmers' organisations, policy makers, representatives of funders, business, innovators, retail and public kitchens etc.). At that meeting, participants are encouraged to apply for new projects in the Organic RDD program (and others). In 2022, they plan to include the subject "how to include stakeholders" in focus, and intend to use the Explorer's Guide as a source of many good ideas on how do to that.
- The EURAKNOS Explorers Guide, videos and podcasts are being used and promoted through the RAU teaching programme to students on the [BSc in Food Environment and Society](#), in a designated module on the Theory and Practice of Knowledge Exchange (10 students).
- RAU is also using the EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide in the co-development of a new consortium for a new Thematic Network proposal.

6. Conclusion

The EURAKNOS consortium has made great efforts to create user friendly, informative dissemination materials which have been made available digitally and in different languages. Partners have promoted the outputs of EURAKNOS to relevant target audiences, with special attention on our key outputs: The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks; policy recommendations (the vision paper and policy brief); and the e-KRP in close collaboration with the EUREKA FarmBook. Combined activities had the potential to reach over 300,000 people.

Through our SIB and KIP, EURAKNOS has created a strong reputation amongst TN and AKIS actors. We have developed good links with EIP-Agri such that EURAKNOS findings will be considered in the development of the EIP-Agri Service point. Due to the overlap between activities and consortia partners in EURAKNOS and EUREKA, the network remains active and EURAKNOS results will continue to be disseminated throughout 2021.

EURAKNOS results are already being successfully exploited in EUREKA, and will be further built upon in a future Horizon Europe funding call. By participating in the Horizon Results Booster Exploitation Strategy Seminar, EURAKNOS has provided a strong foundation including useful considerations for these future projects.